

SOME OPERATIONS OF FUZZY SETS IN UP-ALGEBRAS WITH RESPECT TO A TRIANGULAR NORM

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ABSTRACT. This paper aim is to apply the notions of the intersection and the union of any fuzzy set to UP-algebras. We investigate properties of the intersection and the union of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras, T -fuzzy near UP-filters, T -fuzzy UP-filters, T -fuzzy UP-ideals, T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideals, anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras, and anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters of UP-algebras.

1. INTRODUCTION AND PRELIMINARIES

The branch of the logical algebra, a UP-algebra was introduced by Iampan [4] in 2017, and it is known that the class of KU-algebras [10] is a proper subclass of the class of UP-algebras. It have been examined by several researchers, for example, Somjanta et al. [16] introduced the notion of fuzzy sets in UP-algebras, the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy sets in UP-algebras was introduced by Kesorn et al. [7], Kaijajae et al. [6] introduced the notions of anti-fuzzy UP-ideals and anti-fuzzy UP-subalgebras of UP-algebras, the notion of Q -fuzzy sets in UP-algebras was introduced by Tanamoon et al. [19], Sripaeng et al. [18] introduced the notion anti- Q -fuzzy UP-ideals and anti Q -fuzzy UP-subalgebras of UP-algebras, the notion of \mathcal{N} -fuzzy sets in UP-algebras was introduced by Songsaeng and Iampan [17], Senapati et al. [14, 15] applied cubic set and interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy structure in UP-algebras, Romano [11] introduced the notion of proper UP-filters in UP-algebras, etc.

In this paper, we apply the notions of the intersection and the union of any fuzzy set to UP-algebras. We investigate properties of the intersection and the union of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras, T -fuzzy near UP-filters, T -fuzzy UP-filters, T -fuzzy UP-ideals, T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideals, anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras, and anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters of UP-algebras.

Before we begin our study, we will introduce the definition of a UP-algebra.

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Definition 1.1. [4] An algebra $X = (X, \cdot, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is called a *UP-algebra* where X is a nonempty set, \cdot is a binary operation on X , and 0 is a fixed element of X (i.e., a nullary operation) if it satisfies the following axioms:

$$\text{(UP-1): } (\forall x, y, z \in X)((y \cdot z) \cdot ((x \cdot y) \cdot (x \cdot z)) = 0),$$

$$\text{(UP-2): } (\forall x \in X)(0 \cdot x = x),$$

$$\text{(UP-3): } (\forall x \in X)(x \cdot 0 = 0), \text{ and}$$

$$\text{(UP-4): } (\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot y = 0, y \cdot x = 0 \Rightarrow x = y).$$

From [4], we know that the notion of UP-algebras is a generalization of KU-algebras (see [10]).

Example 1.2. [13] Let X be a universal set and let $\Omega \in \mathcal{P}(X)$ where $\mathcal{P}(X)$ means the power set of X . Let $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(X) = \{A \in \mathcal{P}(X) \mid \Omega \subseteq A\}$. Define a binary operation \cdot on $\mathcal{P}_\Omega(X)$ by putting $A \cdot B = B \cap (A^C \cup \Omega)$ for all $A, B \in \mathcal{P}_\Omega(X)$ where A^C means the complement of a subset A . Then $(\mathcal{P}_\Omega(X), \cdot, \Omega)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the *generalized power UP-algebra of type 1 with respect to Ω* . Let $\mathcal{P}^\Omega(X) = \{A \in \mathcal{P}(X) \mid A \subseteq \Omega\}$. Define a binary operation $*$ on $\mathcal{P}^\Omega(X)$ by putting $A * B = B \cup (A^C \cap \Omega)$ for all $A, B \in \mathcal{P}^\Omega(X)$. Then $(\mathcal{P}^\Omega(X), *, \Omega)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the *generalized power UP-algebra of type 2 with respect to Ω* . In particular, $(\mathcal{P}(X), \cdot, \emptyset)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the *power UP-algebra of type 1*, and $(\mathcal{P}(X), *, X)$ is a UP-algebra and we shall call it the *power UP-algebra of type 2*.

Example 1.3. [3] Let \mathbb{N} be the set of all natural numbers with two binary operations \circ and \bullet defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in \mathbb{N}) \left(x \circ y = \begin{cases} y & \text{if } x < y, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \right)$$

and

$$(\forall x, y \in \mathbb{N}) \left(x \bullet y = \begin{cases} y & \text{if } x > y \text{ or } x = 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \right).$$

Then $(\mathbb{N}, \circ, 0)$ and $(\mathbb{N}, \bullet, 0)$ are UP-algebras.

Example 1.4. [17] Let $A = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$ be a set with a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
0	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
1	0	0	2	3	2	3	6
2	0	1	0	3	1	5	3
3	0	1	2	0	4	1	2
4	0	0	0	3	0	3	3
5	0	0	2	0	2	0	2
6	0	1	0	0	1	1	0

Then $(A, \cdot, 0)$ is a UP-algebra.

For more examples of UP-algebras, see [1, 5, 12, 13].

In a UP-algebra $X = (X, \cdot, 0)$, the following assertions are valid (see [4, 5]).

$$(\forall x \in X)(x \cdot x = 0), \quad (1.1)$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0, y \cdot z = 0 \Rightarrow x \cdot z = 0), \quad (1.2)$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0 \Rightarrow (z \cdot x) \cdot (z \cdot y) = 0), \quad (1.3)$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0 \Rightarrow (y \cdot z) \cdot (x \cdot z) = 0), \quad (1.4)$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot (y \cdot x) = 0), \quad (1.5)$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)((y \cdot x) \cdot x = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = y \cdot x), \quad (1.6)$$

$$(\forall x, y \in X)(x \cdot (y \cdot y) = 0), \quad (1.7)$$

$$(\forall a, x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot (y \cdot z)) \cdot (x \cdot ((a \cdot y) \cdot (a \cdot z))) = 0), \quad (1.8)$$

$$(\forall a, x, y, z \in X)((((a \cdot x) \cdot (a \cdot y)) \cdot z) \cdot ((x \cdot y) \cdot z) = 0), \quad (1.9)$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot y) \cdot z \cdot (y \cdot z) = 0), \quad (1.10)$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)(x \cdot y = 0 \Rightarrow x \cdot (z \cdot y) = 0), \quad (1.11)$$

$$(\forall x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot y) \cdot z \cdot (x \cdot (y \cdot z)) = 0), \text{ and} \quad (1.12)$$

$$(\forall a, x, y, z \in X)((x \cdot y) \cdot z \cdot (y \cdot (a \cdot z)) = 0). \quad (1.13)$$

2. FUZZY SETS WITH RESPECT TO A T-NORM IN UP-ALGEBRAS

Definition 2.1. [20] A *fuzzy set* A in a nonempty set X (or a *fuzzy subset* of X) is described by its membership function α_A . To every point $x \in X$, this function associates a real number $\alpha_A(x)$ in the unit interval $[0, 1]$. The number $\alpha_A(x)$ is interpreted for the point as a degree of belonging x to the fuzzy set A , that is, $A := \{(x, \alpha_A(x)) \mid x \in X\}$. We say that a fuzzy set A in X is *constant* if its membership function α_A is constant.

Definition 2.2. [8] A *triangular norm* (briefly, t-norm) is a binary operation T on the unit interval $[0, 1]$, i.e., a function $T : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ that satisfies the following axioms:

(T1): Boundary condition: $(\forall x \in [0, 1])(T(x, 1) = x)$,

(T2): Commutativity: $(\forall x, y \in [0, 1])(T(x, y) = T(y, x))$,

(T3): Associativity: $(\forall x, y, z \in [0, 1])(T(x, T(y, z)) = T(T(x, y), z))$, and

(T4): Monotonicity: $(\forall x, y, z \in [0, 1])(y \leq z \Rightarrow T(x, y) \leq T(x, z))$.

Let T be a t-norm. Then the following properties hold (see [2]).

$$(\forall x, y \in [0, 1])(T(x, y) \leq x \text{ and } T(x, y) \leq y), \quad (2.1)$$

$$(\forall x \in [0, 1])(T(x, 0) = 0), \quad (2.2)$$

$$(\forall a, b, x, y \in [0, 1])(x \leq a, y \leq b \Rightarrow T(x, y) \leq T(a, b)), \text{ and} \quad (2.3)$$

$$(\forall a, b, x, y \in [0, 1])(x \leq a, y \leq a \Rightarrow T(x, y) \leq a). \quad (2.4)$$

In what follows, let X denote a UP-algebra $(X, \cdot, 0)$ and T a t-norm unless otherwise specified.

Definition 2.3. [2] A fuzzy set A in X is called

- (1) a *T-fuzzy UP-subalgebra* of X if $(\forall x, y \in X)(\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \geq T(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_A(y)))$.
- (2) a *T-fuzzy near UP-filter* of X if
 - (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \geq \alpha_A(x))$, and
 - (ii) $(\forall x, y \in X)(\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \geq T(\alpha_A(y), \alpha_A(y)))$.
- (3) a *T-fuzzy UP-filter* of X if
 - (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \geq \alpha_A(x))$, and

- (ii) $(\forall x, y \in X)(\alpha_A(y) \geq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot y), \alpha_A(x)))$.
- (4) a T -fuzzy UP-ideal of X if
- (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \geq \alpha_A(x))$, and
- (ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\alpha_A(x \cdot z) \geq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), \alpha_A(y)))$.
- (5) a T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideal of X if
- (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \geq \alpha_A(x))$, and
- (ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\alpha_A(x) \geq T(\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), \alpha_A(y)))$.

Burandate et al. [2] proved the generalization that the notion of T -fuzzy UP-ideals is a generalization of T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideals, the notion of T -fuzzy UP-filters is a generalization of T -fuzzy UP-ideals, the notion of T -fuzzy near UP-filters is a generalization of T -fuzzy UP-filters, and the notion of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras is a generalization of T -fuzzy UP-filters. Moreover, the notion of T -fuzzy near UP-filters does not coincide with the notion of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras.

Example 2.4. [2] Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a UP-algebra with a fixed element 0 and a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	2	3	2
2	0	1	0	3	1
3	0	1	2	0	4
4	0	0	0	3	0

Let T_{Luk} be the Łukasiewicz t-norm defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in [0, 1])(T_{\text{Luk}}(x, y) = \max\{x + y - 1, 0\}). \quad (2.5)$$

Define a fuzzy set A in X by

$$\alpha_A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 0.7 & 0.4 & 0.2 & 0.5 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then A is a T_{Luk} -fuzzy UP-ideal of X . Since

$$\alpha_A(2) = 0.2 < 0.4 = T_{\text{Luk}}(\alpha_A((2 \cdot 0) \cdot (2 \cdot 2)), \alpha_A(0)),$$

we have A is not a T_{Luk} -fuzzy strongly UP-ideal of X .

Example 2.5. [2] Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a UP-algebra with a fixed element 0 and a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	2	0	0	0
3	0	2	2	0	0
4	0	2	2	4	0

Define a fuzzy set A in X by

$$\alpha_A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 0.8 & 0.7 & 0.9 & 0.9 & 0.9 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then A is a T_{Luk} -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X (see T_{Luk} in Example 2.4). Since

$$\alpha_A(1) = 0.7 < 0.8 = T_{\text{Luk}}(\alpha_A(4 \cdot 1), \alpha_A(4)),$$

we have A is not a T_{Luk} -fuzzy UP-filter of X . Since $\alpha_A(0) < \alpha_A(2)$, we have A does not satisfy the condition: $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \geq \alpha_A(x))$.

Example 2.6. [2] Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ be a UP-algebra with a fixed element 0 and a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	0	0
2	0	2	0	0	0
3	0	2	2	0	0
4	0	2	2	4	0

Let T_{\min} be the Gödel t-norm defined by

$$(\forall x, y \in [0, 1])(T_{\min}(x, y) = \min\{x, y\}). \quad (2.6)$$

Define a fuzzy set A in X by

$$\alpha_A = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 0.9 & 0.1 & 0.3 & 0.2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then A is a T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X (see T_{\min} in Example 2.5). Since

$$\alpha_A(4 \cdot 3) = 0 < 0.2 = T_{\min}(\alpha_A(3), \alpha_A(3)),$$

we have A is not a T_{\min} -fuzzy near UP-filter of X .

Definition 2.7. [2] A fuzzy set A in X is called

- (1) an *anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra* of X if $(\forall x, y \in X)(\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \leq T(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_A(y)))$.
- (2) an *anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filter* of X if
 - (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \leq \alpha_A(x))$, and
 - (ii) $(\forall x, y \in X)(\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \leq T(\alpha_A(y), \alpha_A(y)))$.
- (3) an *anti- T -fuzzy UP-filter* of X if
 - (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \leq \alpha_A(x))$, and
 - (ii) $(\forall x, y \in X)(\alpha_A(y) \leq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot y), \alpha_A(x)))$.
- (4) an *anti- T -fuzzy UP-ideal* of X if
 - (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \leq \alpha_A(x))$, and
 - (ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\alpha_A(x \cdot z) \leq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), \alpha_A(y)))$.
- (5) an *anti- T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideal* of X if
 - (i) $(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_A(0) \leq \alpha_A(x))$, and
 - (ii) $(\forall x, y, z \in X)(\alpha_A(x) \leq T(\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), \alpha_A(y)))$.

Burandate et al. [2] proved the generalization that the notion of anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters is a generalization of anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras. Moreover, the notions of anti- T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideals, anti- T -fuzzy UP-ideals, anti- T -fuzzy UP-filters, and anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras coincide.

Theorem 2.1. [2] *If A is an anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X , then A is constant.*

3. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we investigate properties of the intersection and the union of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras, T -fuzzy near UP-filters, T -fuzzy UP-filters, T -fuzzy UP-ideals, T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideals, anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras, and anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters of UP-algebras.

Definition 3.1. [9] Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of fuzzy sets in a nonempty set X . Define the *intersection* $\cap \mathcal{A}$ in X by its membership function $\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}$ which defined as follows:

$$(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x) = \inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}). \quad (3.1)$$

Define the *union* $\cup \mathcal{A}$ in X by its membership function $\alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}$ which defined as follows:

$$(\forall x \in X)(\alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(x) = \sup\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}). \quad (3.2)$$

Theorem 3.1. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras of X . Then $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is also a T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X .*

Proof. Let $x, y \in X$. Then $\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \geq T(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_A(y))$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(x)$ and $\inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(y)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows from (2.3) that

$$(\forall A \in \mathcal{A})(T(\inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \leq T(\alpha_A(x), \alpha_A(y)) \leq \alpha_A(x \cdot y)).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x), \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y)) &= T(\inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \\ &\leq \inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \\ &= \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is a T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X . \square

The following example show that the union of T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras of X is not a T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X .

Example 3.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a UP-algebra with a fixed element 0 and a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	2
2	0	1	0	2
3	0	1	0	0

Define two fuzzy sets A_1 and A_2 in X as follows:

$$\alpha_{A_1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.9 & 0.7 & 0.1 & 0.1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

and

$$\alpha_{A_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.8 & 0.4 & 0.5 & 0.6 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then A_1 and A_2 are T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-subalgebras of X (see T_{\min} in Example 2.6). We thus obtain the union of A_1 and A_2 as follows:

$$\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.9 & 0.7 & 0.5 & 0.6 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since

$$\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(1 \cdot 3) = 0.5 < 0.6 = T_{\min}(\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(1), \alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(3)).$$

Therefore, $\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(x)$ is not a T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X .

Theorem 3.2. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of T -fuzzy near UP-filters of X . Then $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is also a T -fuzzy near UP-filter of X .*

Proof. Let $x \in X$. Since $\alpha_A(0) \geq \alpha_A(x)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, we have

$$\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(0) = \inf\{\alpha_A(0)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \geq \inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} = \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x).$$

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \geq T(\alpha_A(y), \alpha_A(y))$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(y)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows from (2.3) that

$$(\forall A \in \mathcal{A})(T(\inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \leq T(\alpha_A(y), \alpha_A(y)) \leq \alpha_A(x \cdot y)).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y), \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y)) &= T(\inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \\ &\leq \inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \\ &= \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is a T -fuzzy near UP-filter of X . □

Theorem 3.3. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of T -fuzzy UP-filters of X . Then $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is also a T -fuzzy UP-filter of X .*

Proof. The proof of the first statement is similar to the proof of Theorem 3.2. Let $x, y \in X$. Then $\alpha_A(y) \geq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot y), \alpha_A(x))$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(x \cdot y)$ and $\inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(x)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows from (2.3) that

$$(\forall A \in \mathcal{A})(T(\inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \leq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot y), \alpha_A(x)) \leq \alpha_A(y)).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot y), \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x)) &= T(\inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \\ &\leq \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \\ &= \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is a T -fuzzy UP-filter of X . □

The following example show that the union of T -fuzzy UP-filters of X is not a T -fuzzy UP-filter.

Example 3.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a UP-algebra with a fixed element 0 and a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	2
2	0	1	0	1
3	0	0	0	0

Define two fuzzy sets A_1 and A_2 in X as follows:

$$\alpha_{A_1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

and

$$\alpha_{A_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.8 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then A_1 and A_2 are T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-filter of X (see T_{\min} in Example 2.6). We thus obtain the union of A_1 and A_2 as follows:

$$\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.8 & 0.5 & 0.4 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Since

$$\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(3) = 0.3 < 0.4 = T_{\min}(\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(1 \cdot 3), \alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(1)).$$

Therefore, $\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(x)$ is not a T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-filter of X .

Theorem 3.4. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of T -fuzzy UP-ideals of X . Then $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is also a T -fuzzy UP-ideal of X .*

Proof. The proof of the first statement is similar to the proof of Theorem 3.2. Let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $\alpha_A(x \cdot z) \geq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), \alpha_A(y))$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z))\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z))$ and $\inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(y)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows from (2.3) that

$$\begin{aligned} (\forall A \in \mathcal{A})(T(\inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z))\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) &\leq T(\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), \alpha_A(y)) \\ &\leq \alpha_A(x \cdot z). \end{aligned}$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot (y \cdot z)), \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y)) &= T(\inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot (y \cdot z))\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \\ &\leq \inf\{\alpha_A(x \cdot z)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \\ &= \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot z). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is a T -fuzzy UP-ideal of X . \square

The following example show that the union of T -fuzzy UP-ideals of X is not a T -fuzzy UP-ideal.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ be a UP-algebra with a fixed element 0 and a binary operation \cdot defined by the following Cayley table:

\cdot	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	0	0	2	2
2	0	1	0	1
3	0	0	0	0

Define two fuzzy sets A_1 and A_2 in X as follows:

$$\alpha_{A_1} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.4 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

and

$$\alpha_{A_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.8 & 0.5 & 0.2 & 0.2 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Then A_1 and A_2 are T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-ideal of X (see T_{\min} in Example 2.6). We thus obtain the union of A_1 and A_2 as follows:

$$\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 0.8 & 0.5 & 0.4 & 0.3 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Therefore, $\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(x)$ is not a T_{\min} -fuzzy UP-ideal of X because

$$\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(0 \cdot 3) = 0.3 < 0.4 = T_{\min}(\alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(0 \cdot (2 \cdot 3)), \alpha_{A_1 \cup A_2}(2)).$$

Theorem 3.5. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideals of X . Then $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is also a T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideal of X .*

Proof. The proof of the first statement is similar to the proof of Theorem 3.2. Let $x, y, z \in X$. Then $\alpha_A(x) \geq T(\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), \alpha_A(y))$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\inf\{\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x))\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x))$ and $\inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \alpha_A(y)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows from (2.3) that

$$(\forall A \in \mathcal{A})(T(\inf\{\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x))\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \leq T(\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), \alpha_A(y)) \leq \alpha_A(x)).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x)), \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y)) &= T(\inf\{\alpha_A((z \cdot y) \cdot (z \cdot x))\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \inf\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \\ &\leq \inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \\ &= \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is a T -fuzzy strongly UP-ideal of X . \square

Theorem 3.6. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras (is also anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters) of X . Then $\cup \mathcal{A}$ is also an anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X .*

Proof. By Theorem 2.1, we have $\alpha_A(x) = \alpha_A(0)$ for all $x \in X$. Then $\alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(x) = \sup\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} = \alpha_A(0)$. Let $x, y \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot y) &= \alpha_A(0) \\ &= \alpha_A(0 \cdot 0) && \text{((UP-2))} \\ &\leq T(\alpha_A(0), \alpha_A(0)) && \text{(Definition 2.7 (2) (ii))} \\ &= T(\alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(x), \alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(y)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cup \mathcal{A}$ is an anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X . \square

Theorem 3.7. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebras (is also anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters) of X . Then $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is also an anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X .*

Proof. By Theorem 2.1, we have $\alpha_A(x) = \alpha_A(0)$ for all $x \in X$. Then $\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x) = \inf\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} = \alpha_A(0)$. Let $x, y \in X$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot y) &= \alpha_A(0) \\ &= \alpha_A(0 \cdot 0) && \text{((UP-2))} \\ &\leq T(\alpha_A(0), \alpha_A(0)) && \text{(Definition 2.7 (2) (ii))} \\ &= T(\alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(x), \alpha_{\cap \mathcal{A}}(y)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cap \mathcal{A}$ is an anti- T -fuzzy UP-subalgebra of X . \square

Theorem 3.8. *Let \mathcal{A} be a nonempty family of anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filters of X . Then $\cup \mathcal{A}$ is also an anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filter of X .*

Proof. Let $x \in X$. Since $\alpha_A(0) \leq \alpha_A(x)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, we have

$$\alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(0) = \sup\{\alpha_A(0)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \leq \sup\{\alpha_A(x)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} = \alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(x).$$

Let $x, y \in X$. Then $\alpha_A(x \cdot y) \leq T(\alpha_A(y), \alpha_A(y))$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\sup\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \geq \alpha_A(y)$ for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$, it follows from (2.3) that

$$(\forall A \in \mathcal{A})(T(\sup\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \sup\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \geq T(\alpha_A(y), \alpha_A(y)) \geq \alpha_A(x \cdot y)).$$

Thus

$$\begin{aligned} T(\alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(y), \alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(y)) &= T(\sup\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}, \sup\{\alpha_A(y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}}) \\ &\geq \sup\{\alpha_A(x \cdot y)\}_{A \in \mathcal{A}} \\ &= \alpha_{\cup \mathcal{A}}(x \cdot y). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\cup \mathcal{A}$ is an anti- T -fuzzy near UP-filter of X . \square

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